

Synthesis and antimicrobial evaluation of thiosemicarbazones

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Manuscript received 11 July 2001, accepted 25 September 2001

Some new thiosemicarbazones (2-7) have been synthesized via condensation of piperidone 1, thiosemicarbazide and some acylating agents. Majority of the compounds showed significant antimicrobial activity.

Thiosemicarbazones possess various biological activities. Some new thiosemicarbazones have been synthesized and screened for possible antimicrobial activities. Condensation of 4-fluorobenzaldehyde, ammonium hydroxide and methyl ethyl ketone in the presence of ammonium acetate and 99% ethanol gave 2,6-bis(4-fluorophenyl)-3-methyl-4-piperidone (1). 1 on reaction with thiosemicarbazide in ethanol gave 2,6-bis(4-fluorophenyl)-3-methyl-4-piperidone thiosemicarbazone (2). Five new thiosemicarbazones (3-7) were synthesized.

All the compounds were tested for their antimicrobial activities by disc-diffusion method² at an amount of 30 µg/disc. Ciprofloxacin and amphotericin B were used as the reference compounds for antibacterial and antifungal activities, respectively. *Staphylococcus aureus* (Gram positive bacterium), *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Gram negative bacteria) and *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans* (fungi) were used as test organisms. Activity indices (a.i.) reveal that antipseudomonal activity of compound 6 is comparable to that of ciprofloxacin. Compounds 2, 4 and 5 showed potent activities than amphotericin B against *A. niger*. The antibacterial activity of the compounds may be due to the presence of thiosemicarbazone group, sulfonyl group and the substituted benzoyl group.

Experimental

TLC was run on a silica gel GF₂₅₄ (E. Merck) aluminium foil plates using methanol and strong ammonia (100 : 1.5) as mobile phase and the spots were detected by UV-light. M.p.s. were determined by Veego apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 6000 FTIR spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR spectra on a Varian (90 MHz) spectrophotometer using TMS as internal standard.

Compound 1 : Ammonium acetate (0.5 mol) in 99%

ethanol (50 ml) was mixed with 4-fluorobenzaldehyde (0.1 mol), methyl ethyl ketone (0.05 mol) and strong ammonia solution (30 ml). The reaction mixture was boiled for 1 h and cooled at room temperature. Then conc. HCl (30 ml) was added to it and the resulting solid was crystallized from aqueous ethanol, (65%), m.p. 312-315°; ν_{\max} 3116 (N-H), 1790 (C=O), 1339 cm⁻¹ (C-F); δ (CDCl₃) 0.7 (3H, d, *J* 8.7 Hz), 2.5 (2H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz), 3.4 (1H, q, *J* 4.4 Hz), 3.9 (1H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz), 6.8 (1H, t, *J* 6.5 Hz), 7.2 (8H, m).

Compound 2 : A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol) and thiosemicarbazide (0.01 mol) in ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 3 h with stirring. The contents were then cooled and poured into crushed ice. The resulting

- 2 H
- 3 OCC₆H₅
- 4 OCC₆H₄NO₂
- 5 OCC₆H₄OH
- 6 OCC₆H₄Cl
- 7 O₂SC₆H₄CH₃

Scheme 1

Note

solid was washed with water and crystallized from aqueous ethanol, (71%), m.p. 228–230°, ν_{\max} 3257 (N–H), 1509 (NHC=S), 1294 (C–F), 1222 cm^{-1} (C=S); δ (DMSO- d_6) 0.7 (3H, d, J 8.7 Hz), 2.4 (2H, d, J 7.5 Hz), 3.4 (1H, q, J 4.4 Hz), 6.9 (3H, m), 7.3 (8H, m).

Compounds 3–7 : Compound 2 was heated with an equimolar amount of acylating or sulfonylating reagent (benzoyl chloride, 4-nitrobenzoyl chloride, 4-hydroxybenzoyl chloride, 4-chlorobenzoyl chloride and *p*-toluenesulfonyl chloride) in 10% (w/v) aqueous sodium bicarbonate (20 ml). The reaction mixture was shaken vigorously for 10 min until the odour of reagents disappeared. The solid products obtained were then crystallized from ethanol : **3** (59%), m.p. 105–107°; ν_{\max} 3175 (N–H), 1682 (C=O), 1619 (NHC=S), 1376 (NHC=S), 1294 (C–F), 1222 cm^{-1} (C=S); δ (DMSO- d_6) 1.8 (2H, d, J 7 Hz), 2.4 (2H, d, J 7.5 Hz), 4.8–5.5 (3H, m), 7.2–7.8 (13H, m); **4** (67%), 132–135°; ν_{\max} 3180 (N–H), 1662 (C=O), 1622 (NHC=S), 1381 (NHC=S), 1319 (C–F), 1214 cm^{-1} (C=S); δ (DMSO- d_6) 1.8 (2H, d, J 7 Hz), 2.4 (2H, d, J 7.5 Hz), 4.8–5.5 (3H, m), 7.2–7.9 (13H, m); **5** (64%), 165–167°; ν_{\max} 3178 (N–H), 1676 (C=O),

1626 (NHC=S), 1378 (NHC=S), 1320 (C–F), 1202 cm^{-1} (C=S); δ (DMSO- d_6) 1.8 (2H, d, J 7 Hz), 2.4 (2H, d, J 7.5 Hz), 4.1 (1H, s), 4.8–5.5 (3H, m), 7.2–7.9 (13H, m); **6** (68%), 174–176°; ν_{\max} 3182 (N–H), 1670 (C=O), 1614 (NHC=S), 1384 (NHC=S), 1343 (C–F), 1195 cm^{-1} (C=S); δ (DMSO- d_6) 1.8 (2H, d, J 7 Hz), 2.4 (2H, d, J 7.5 Hz), 4.8–5.5 (3H, m), 7.2–7.9 (13H, m); **7** (63%), 42–45°; ν_{\max} 3543 (N–H), 1616 (C=O), 1373 (NHC=S), 1293 (NHC=S), 1193 (C=S), 1045 cm^{-1} (S=O); δ (DMSO- d_6) 2.1 (2H, d, J 7 Hz), 6.8 (3H, m), 7.3 (12H, m).

All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

References

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